

Principals' Management Strategies as Correlates of Teachers' Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State

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Abstract

The increasing display of public dissatisfaction, resentment and anger over the appalling state of moral ineptitude and academic backwardness that have characterized Nigerian secondary schools in recent times especially in Enugu State is worrisome. The absenteeism and lackadaisical attitude and examination malpractices have become common features of many public secondary schools in Enugu State. This prompted the study which is to analyze the principals' management strategies as correlates of teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested. Correlation survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 8,644 teachers from 292 public secondary schools in the six Education zones in Enugu State. The simple random sampling was used to draw 863 teachers in the 292 public schools in Enugu State. A 10-item questionnaire titled "Principals' Management Strategies Rating Scale (PMSRS) and 20-item questionnaire titled "Teachers' Effective Teaching Rating Scale" (TETRS) respectively were the instruments for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The overall coefficient of 0.90 was obtained. The researchers with the help of five research assistants collected the data for the study. Pearson 'r' as a linear correlation was used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at $P < 0.05$ level of significance. The findings of the study among others revealed that Principals' management strategies are a significant correlate of teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Based on the findings it was recommended among others that principals should give priority to teachers' discipline since it affects teachers' effectiveness.

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15120288](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15120288)

Background to the Study

The role of education as a veritable tool for growth, development and advancement of any society cannot be over-emphasized. The federal Government of Nigeria had adopted education as an instrument for effecting national development and social change (FRN 2013). The Nigeria's educational system makes secondary education a link between the primary and higher education. The goals of Secondary education include but not limited to preparing the students for useful living in the society, inculcation of permanent literacy skills beyond what is offered at primary schools and preparing the learners for higher education.

These laudable goals of secondary education cannot be achieved without the teachers. They (teachers) occupy very strategic position in ensuring that the expected quality instructional delivery is impacted on the students. The teachers remain one of the major influential factors in the implementation of any school curriculum. While describing the role of the teachers in maintaining a functional educational system, the National Policy on Education states that "No education system can rise above the quality of its teachers (FGN, 2013). Therefore the quality of any level of education, including the secondary, depends largely on the teachers' effectiveness.

Teachers' effectiveness encompasses the dynamic and interactive process of creating, adapting, and negotiating learning environments that support all students' activities that improve learning. Chikendu (2022) posited that teacher effectiveness is a predictor of secondary school students' academic achievement.

Teacher effectiveness is determined by not just what the teacher does; but also what the teacher has achieved. In other words students' learning and their perceptions about the teacher also determine teachers' teaching effectiveness.

Several factors can influence teachers' effective teaching in secondary schools. One of such factors is principals' management strategies. Management involves decision making at various levels of organization for getting things done by others (Cassomb, 2016). In educational organizations, the onus of managing schools for realization of educational objectives rest on the principal. In order to achieve optimum results, the principal should be skilled in management. It is his duty to ensure that goals of educational policies and programs are realized. He performs

managerial functions such as planning organizing, directing, coordinating, communication, motivation. Specifically his functions/roles include: establishing of healthy school climate and culture; curriculum instructor development and improvement; provision and maintenance of school plant facilities; and instructional and non- instructional supervision. Principals can only manage human and material resources effectively if he has clear view, understanding and application of the appropriate management strategies.

Omemu (2017) stated that principals' management strategy is concerned with shaping an organization in the right path towards the achievement of its goals. Some of the management strategies of the principals include: disciplining strategy and participatory decision making strategy.

Discipline as a generally acceptable behavioural conduct in public educational institutions is concerned with rights and corrective duty. Discipline is the maintenance of quality of the atmosphere necessary for achievement of the school goals (Ebuara & Coker; 2012). In well-disciplined school, the principal provides clear and broad-based rules, delegate disciplinary matters and ensure commitment and discipline on the part of teachers to establish and maintain appropriate students' behaviour. Ensuring discipline in schools depends on the ability of the school principal to intelligently utilize the various approaches of staff discipline in order to ensure compliance the codes of good behaviour.

Another principals' management strategy which is of interest to this study is participatory decision-making. This can be seen as the process of involving the staff members in selecting the most preferred and workable action among other options or alternative courses of action available, either towards solving problems or the achievement of an objective (Akhiemien and Oriomah, 2023). This can only occur in an enabling environment where the principal possesses a high level of imagination, initiative, vision, and techniques in making a decision which will equally help in improving the quality and effectiveness of the staff members.

Principals' management strategies are meant to enhance effective teaching which would produce students of higher academic performance. However, the researcher has observed the existence of low teacher morale, low teacher motivation by principals, poor attitude to work, lack of interest in teaching as well as poor instructional planning and delivery in secondary schools in Enugu state. All these are symptoms of poor application of management strategies by the principals.

This appears to be the reason for the steady decline in teachers' effectiveness as there are cases of poor teaching and learning process and poor teaching and learning outcome in public secondary schools in Enugu State. This noticeable nosedive in teacher effectiveness may be attributed to the poor application of management strategies by principals in public secondary schools in Enugu State. It is against this backdrop that this study will determine the relationship between principals' management strategies and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Observations made by the researchers have shown that there is increasing display of public dissatisfaction, resentment and anger over the appalling state of moral ineptitude and academic backwardness that have characterized Nigerian secondary schools in recent times. The situation is even more worrisome in Enugu State, where cases of students' absenteeism, lackadaisical attitude and examination malpractices have become common features of public secondary schools. Time and again, students come to school very late and leave before school dismissal time. This leaves the researchers to question the management strategies used by some of the principals in running the affairs of the schools, as they are the sole facilitators of academic excellence in the public secondary schools in the state.

More so, the researchers have equally encountered students complaining about teachers' activities in the school especially on issues that are related to teaching ineffectiveness, such as poor performance of their duties, as some of them are not punctual to work (some teachers show laissez faire attitude to work by coming very late to school and leaving before school dismissal), absenteeism from school, exhibition of poor classroom management, lack of instructional supervision, lack of discipline and sometimes incompetency in pedagogical skills. These issues have been very controversial as they generate argument between teachers and parents.

One begins to wonder if these situations are attributable to principals' management strategies in secondary schools in Enugu State. This is the basis of this study and forms the problem which is also posed as a question: what is the relationship between principals' management strategies and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State?

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to ascertain the relationship between principals' management strategies and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Specifically, the study established the relationship between principals' use of:

1. Discipline strategy and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State.
2. Participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the nature of relationship between principals' use of discipline strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools in Enugu State?
2. What is the nature of relationship between principals' use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between principals' use of discipline strategy and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between principals' use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Method

A correlation survey design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 8,644 teachers from 292 public secondary schools of the six Education zones in Enugu State. The sample for the study is 863 teachers representing ten percent of the entire population. The instruments for collection of data were researcher's developed instruments titled: Principals' Management Strategies Rating Scale (PMSRS) and Teachers' Effective Teaching Rating Scale (TETRS). To ascertain the face validity of the instrument for the study, the researcher submitted the instruments together with the research topic, purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses to two experts in Department of Educational Management and Policy and one expert

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Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15120288](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15120288)

in the Department of Education Foundation, all from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. These experts were requested to validate the instrument relative to the appropriateness of the structure, instructions, item statements and content coverage and freely modify the sections as they deem fit. Based on the corrections and recommendations of by the experts, the final draft of the instrument was made. In order to establish the reliability of the instruments, copies of the instruments were trial-tested with 20 teachers in state government secondary schools in Anambra State. The responses of the respondents were collated to determine the internal consistency of the items in each section of the instruments and this was done using Cronbach's alpha method. The reliability co-efficients for PMSRS and TETRS were 0.89 and 0.74 respectively. The researchers administered copies of the instruments directly on the respondents with the help of five research assistants who are secondary school teachers. Out of 861 copies of questionnaire distributed for data collection, 841 copies were retrieved; this means that 97% retrieval rate.

For the analysis of data, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Descriptive statistics (Pearson "r" as a linear correlation) was used for the research questions. That is, research questions were answered using linear correlation statistics; Pearson "r". This statistics helped to establish the linear relationship between the variables in this study. For the test of hypotheses, the associated inferential statistics (t-test of significance of simple linear correlation) was employed. That is, hypotheses were tested using t-test of significance of simple linear correlation to ascertain the significance of the relationship in the study. $P < 0.05$ level of significance were stated for all the hypotheses.

For the research questions, the coefficient (r) and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the following: 0.00=no relationship, 0.01-0.20=very low relationship, 0.21-0.40=low relationship, 0.41-0.60=moderate relationship, 0.61-0.80=high relationship, 0.81-0.99=very high relationship and 1.00=perfect relationship. For the hypotheses, the acceptance or rejection of null hypotheses were based on the t-cal value and t-tab value. This means that when the t-calculated value is greater than the t-tabulated value, the null hypothesis was rejected but if otherwise, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the nature of relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools?

Table 1: Summaries of descriptive statistics for the nature of relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy (X) and teachers’ effective teaching (Y) in public secondary schools

V	n	Σ	R	r^2	$\%r^2$	Remarks
X	841	5221	0.52	0.2704	27.04	Moderate Positive Relationship
Y	841	20597				

Size (n), Summation (Σ), Simple Linear Correlation (r), Coefficient of Determination (r^2), Percentage Coefficient of Determination ($\%r^2$) and Remarks

The explanation for the calculated nature of relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effectiveness in public secondary schools is presented on Table 1. An apparent view of the table shows that the calculated relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools is 0.52, which indicates a moderate positive relationship. The positive sign shows that an increase in one variable could lead to the same measure of increase in the other variable, implying a parallel relationship between the two variables. The percentage coefficient of determination is obtained as 27.04, indicating that holding other factors constant, the two variables can account for variation in each other with 27.04% certainty. The answer that can be derived from the above question is that there is a moderate positive relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools.

Research Question 2: What is the nature of relationship between principals’ use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools?

Table 2: Summaries of descriptive statistics for the nature of relationship between principals’ use of participatory decision making strategy (X) and teachers’ effective teaching (Y) in public secondary schools

V	N	Σ	R	r^2	$\%r^2$	Remarks
X	841	5058	0.59	0.3481	34.81	Moderate Positive Relationship
Y	841	20597				

Size (n), Summation (Σ), Simple Linear Correlation (r), Coefficient of Determination (r^2), Percentage Coefficient of Determination ($\%r^2$) and Remarks

The explanation for the calculated nature of relationship between principals’ use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools is

presented on Table 2. An apparent view of the table shows that the calculated relationship between principals’ use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools is 0.59, which indicates a moderate positive relationship. The positive sign shows that an increase in one variable could lead to the same measure of increase in the other variable, implying a parallel relationship between the two variables. The percentage coefficient of determination is obtained as 34.81, indicating that holding other factors constant, the two variables can account for variation in each other with 34.81% certainty. The answer that can be derived from the above question is that there is a moderate positive relationship between principals’ use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools.

Hypothesis 1: The relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools was not significant.

Table 3: Summaries of inferential/test statistics for the relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools

V	N	Σ	r	A	Df	t _{cal}	t _{tab}	Decision
X	841	5221	0.52	0.05	839	11.995	1.96	Fail to Accept Ho ₁
Y	841	20597						

The explanation for the test of the significance of the relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools is presented on Table 3. The result indicates the degree of freedom as 839 and the t-calculated value of 11.995 is greater than the t-tabulated value of 1.96. Since the-calculated value is greater than the t-tabulated value, the researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis; thus concluding that the moderate relationship between principals’ use of discipline strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools is significant.

Hypothesis 2: The relationship between principals’ use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools was not significant.

Table 4: Summaries of inferential/test statistics for the relationship between principals’ use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers’ effective teaching in public secondary schools

V	N	Σ	R	A	df	t _{cal}	t _{tab}	Decision
X	841	5058	0.59	0.05	839	14.275	1.96	Fail to Accept Ho ₂
Y	841	20597						

The explanation for the test of the significance of the relationship between principals' use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools is presented on Table 4. The result indicates the degree of freedom as 839 and the t-calculated value of 14.275 is greater than the t-tabulated value of 1.96. Since the-calculated value is greater than the t-tabulated value, the researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis; thus concluding that the moderate relationship between principals' use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools is significant.

Nature of relationship between principals' use of discipline strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools

The finding from this study revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between principals' use of discipline strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools. The inference derived from the findings indicates that the moderate relationship between principals' use of discipline strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools is significant. This shows a remarkable influence of principals' use of discipline strategy on teachers' effective teaching. This finding is true because, when the principals diligently use discipline strategy on the teachers, it will result to improved teachers' effective teaching. This finding is in line with the Umi, Edi and Tahrin (2021) who observed that the combination of principals' leadership and discipline on the teachers has a direct impact on teacher success. The similarity in the findings of the two studies may be attributed to time proximity, similar research design and the same level of education where the studies were conducted. The finding of this study is equally consistent with the result of Gita, Joko, Ali, Siti and Maya (2024) which shows that the variable of discipline has an effect on teacher performance and that the variables of discipline, motivation and compensation all together have a significant relationship with teacher performance. The similarity in the results of both studies further confirms time tested and well-established knowledge in human resource management particularly as it concerns discipline and human behaviour. Again, proximity in time of the two studies may account for the consistency in the results.

Nature of relationship between principals' use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools

The study also revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between principals' use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools. The inference derived from it is that the moderate relationship between principals' use of participatory decision making strategy and teachers' effective teaching in public secondary schools is significant. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Exaudi and Michaela (2022) whose study demonstrated that there is a relationship between teachers' participation in decision making as it increases efficiency and commitment. These findings imply that principals should know that teachers are reliable instruments in implementing administrative policies through their involvement and participation in decision making process. Teachers feel highly motivated when they are consulted about decisions that concern their work. The finding of this study is equally consistent with the finding of Newman (2012) whose study shows that insignificant teacher participation in critical school issues resulted in low commitment and low job satisfaction. This implies that school heads need to consider other people's concerns because if people are angry regarding the way decisions are taken, such decisions will not proceed smoothly. Their feelings and perceptions will account for the success or failure of the decision.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that the relationship between principals' use of discipline strategy, participatory decision making and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools is moderate and positive.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals should give priority to teachers' discipline since it affects teachers' effectiveness.
2. Teachers should be given the chance and opportunity to contribute to decisions making in schools, because most of the school activities concern them.

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